

Supp Figure-Z1

A.

B.

C.

Supp Figure-Z2

Supp Figure-Z3

Supp Figure-Z4

Supp Figure-Z5

A. ERPR +ve HER2-ve

B. ERPR+veHER2+ve

C. ERPR-veHER2+ve

D. Triple negative

Supp Figure-Z6

Supp Figure-Z7

Supp Figure-Z8

Supp Figure-Z9

Supp Figure- Z10

Suppl Figure-Z12

A.

A.

NO

Supp Figure-Z15

NPlus

